

A STUDY ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR OF JUNK FOOD AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Junk foods which has low nutrient content but is high in sugar, salt, oily, spicy, fats, food additives and preservatives. In this paper, an attempt has been made to determine consumers behaviour of junk foods among college students in Coimbatore District. A sample of 100 respondent's was randomly selected from Coimbatore District. The selected samples are analyzed using chi-square test, correlation analysis test and Friedman ranking test. It is found that three variables namely gender, type of family, family income are found to be significant association with consumer behavior of junk foods among college students. The study also finds that family income have significant association with college students behavior towards junk foods.

Key Words: Consumer, Junk, Food, Products, College, Students, Behaviour, Problems, etc.,

Introduction:

In both developed and developing countries is increasing popularity of so called "junk food", which is the most important changes in nutrition patterns. Junk foods which has low nutrient content but is high in salt, sugar and fats, food additives and preservatives. Junk food is rather inexpensive, easy to preserve and widely available around the world. Junk food is a food items that is prepared and served quickly at outlets called fast food shops. It includes French fries, chicken nuggets, pizza, ice-cream, chips, sandwiches, burgers, fried chicken, French fries, chicken nuggets, pizza, ice-cream etc. It is high in calorie, oily, spicy and lacks in micronutrients. Junk foods has been proved many times that its intake leads to many diseases and disorders like obesity which is likely to cause cardiovascular diseases later on. According to World Health Organisation (WHO) frequent junk food consumption is also a health concern because most fast foods are rich in saturated fats, trans fats, simple carbohydrates and sodium-all of which are nutrients associated with hypertension cardiovascular diseases, and many other digestive problems. Junk food culture is a tremendously uprising trend among the college students and professional students are no exception to it. Due to increased study load negatively influences the food choices of students towards junk foods.

Review of Literature:

Sequeira, A. H. and Sowmya, A. and Thomas, Beryl and Mahajan, Chahat and Kumar, Chandra, (2014), investigated the junk food consumption behaviour among college students is identified to have an in depth analysis of food consumption trends and attitudes among college students. The study is based on exploratory approach and primary data are collected from sample using quota sampling to arrive the conclusions. A self administered questionnaire was used to collect the data. Chi-square and Z-test were used to analyse the survey data. Findings of the study concludes that the tendency of replacing regular meals with junk food was more with female students.

S. Steffi and R. Mary Josephine (2013), explored the trend of having food related life styles among the college students. The main objective of the study is to identify their socio demographic characteristics and investigate the difference in attitude towards fast food and normal food. The Questionnaire survey was conducted with 110 female fast food and homemade food users ranging in age from 18-24 years. According to the sample data obtained from the questionnaire, the average females prefer homemade food. In this study the researcher identified the significant differences were found among the six segments in terms of socio-demographic characteristics and attitudes to fast food and normal food. The frequency of distribution of food related segments was 28% fast food, 82% homemade food respectively. Hence the researcher concludes that age group young females is associated with substantially increased usage for homemade food than the fast food.

Vijay Shree, R. R. Prasad, Sanjay Kumar, Setu Sinha and Sanjay Kumar Choudhary (2018), to identify the fast food consumption pattern by the medical students and to evaluate various factors contributing to fast food consumption by the students. In this study a cross sectional study was done among 120 undergraduate medical students of IGIMS, Patna for a period of 6 months. In this study data collection was done using pre-tested structured questionnaire and was analysed using SPSS latest version. The study concludes that majority (88.3%) being aware of the fact that consuming fast food leads to many diseases and disability, all the subjects continue to consume fast food, mostly due to reasons of taste, company and to avoid wastage of time.

Need for the Study:

To investigate the consumers behavior of junk foods among college students in Coimbatore District

Objectives of the Study:

- To know the consumers behaviour of junk foods among college students.
- To determine consumers behaviour of junk foods among college students in Coimbatore District.

Research Methodology:

Coimbatore District is the study area selected for this research. Primary data is collected through well-structured questionnaire. A sample of 100 students in Coimbatore District have been selected by random sampling method. The collected information were reviewed and consolidated into a master table. For the purpose of analysis the data were further processed by using statistical tools.

The Statistical Tools are

- Simple Percentage
- Chi-Square Test
- Friedman Ranking Test
- Correlation Analysis

Limitations of the Study:

- The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.
- The study is restricted to the selected sample of Coimbatore District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Profile of the Respondents:

Table 1 describes the demographic profile of the college students are taken for the study. Out of 100 college students who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (53%) of the respondents are male, most (47%) of the respondents are graduates, (63%) respondents have joint family, the family income of (38%) respondents is between Rs.10,001 to Rs.25,000.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Factors	Number of Respondents N=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	53	53
Female	47	47
Educational Qualification		
Graduate	47	47
PG	28	28
Professional	15	15
Diploma	10	10
Type of Family		
Joint Family	63	63
Nuclear Family	37	37
Family Income		
Up to Rs.10000	35	35
Rs.10000 to Rs.25000	38	38
Above Rs.25000	27	27

Consumer Behavior of the Respondents:

Table 2 describes the consumer behavior of junk foods among college students. Out of 100 respondents who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (47%) of the respondents eat junk foods weekly, (43%) of the respondents eating behavior was influenced through Social Media, most (50%) of the respondents prefer fried chicken and (38%) respondents have their junk food at evening time.

Table 2: Buying Behavior of the Respondents

Factors	Number of Respondents N=200	Percentage
Frequency of eating junk foods		
Daily	26	26
Weekly	47	47
Monthly	27	27
Factors Influence		
Family	22	22
Friends	34	34
Social Media	43	43

Preferred Fast Food		
Pizza	28	28
Burger	22	22
Fried Chicken	50	50
Time Consumption for Junk Food		
Break Fast	16	16
Lunch	14	14
Evening	38	38
Dinner	32	32

Table 3: Relationship between College Students Demographic Profile and Consumer's behavior towards Junk Foods

Variables	χ^2 Value	Table Value	Remarks
Gender	6.534	5.991	S
Educational Qualification	7.178	9.488	NS
Type of Family	6.135	5.991	S
Family Income	10.765	9.488	S

* Significant at 5% percent level

Relationship between Demographic Profile and Consumer Awareness towards FMCG Products of the Respondents:

Table 3 depicts the relationship between selected demographic variables and Consumer's behavior towards Junk Foods of the respondents. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is less than the table value at five percent level, there does not exist any significant association between educational qualification and consumer behaviour towards junk foods of the respondents. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five percent level, there exists a significant association between gender, type of family, family income and consumer behavior towards Junk foods of the respondents. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 4: Consumers Behaviour of Junk Foods Friedman Rank Test

Factors	Average Rank	Rank
Easily Available	2.65	4
Low Price	1.73	5
Spicy/ Tasty	4.78	1
Shop Convenience	3.12	3
Variety of Choice	3.89	2

The above table shows about the Friedman Rank Test for college student's behavior of junk foods were the level of significance is at 0.000 which shows that there is a relationship between the ranks given. It shows that low spicy/ tasty was the first preference factor of the respondents to buy junk foods. Variety of choice was ranked as the second factor to buy junk foods, shop convenience was ranked as third factor, easy available was ranked as fourth factor, and low price was the fifth factor which was preferred by the respondents to buy junk foods.

Table 5: Consumers Behaviour Associated With Demographic Variables-Correlation Analysis

Factors	R	r2
Gender	0.029	0
Educational Qualification	0.058	0.005
Family Income	0.288**	0.07
Type of Family	0.079	0.008

* Significant at five percent level

** Significant at one percent level

Monthly Income:

The correlation analysis shows that these two variables are positively correlated indicating that as the family income increases the level of junk food buying behavior of the respondents also increases. The coefficient of determination (r2) shows that family income of the respondents account for 7 percent of variations in the level of buying at one percent level of significance.

Conclusion:

In India, there are millions of college students are consuming junk foods. The study revealed that majority of the college students being aware of the fact that consuming junk food leads to many diseases. The students continue to consume fast food mostly because they found it tasty. The study also concludes that students like to eat in groups, especially with friends, classmates and also to spend time. It also found that some students were not even aware of the nutritional information of the junk food they consume.

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